

DUCTILITY FROM FIBRES AND MATRIX – LESSONS FROM NATURAL FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Natural fibre composites e.g. wood can display enormous ductility. This ductility is achieved through judicious placement of fibril orientations in the cell walls of plants and also through combination with other polymers (other than cellulose). The primary cell wall of plants is typically a random fibrous network. This talk will discuss the interesting enhanced ductility effects that can be obtained from random nanofibrous networks. It will be shown that it might be possible to obtain double curvature using auxetic effects. In addition to this some recent work on nucleating crazing in amorphous polymers using cellulose nanofibers will be reviewed. The crazing effect is shown to enormously enhance ductility leading to pronounced air scattering and stress whitening of the polymer.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellulose fibres are hierarchical structural composites within themselves. They typically comprise a multilayered structure, with helically wound cellulose nanofibrils (called ‘microfibrils’ in the literature) making up the main load bearing portion of the fibre. Cellulose fibres can also be used to form networks, the most common of these being paper. In addition to this fibres may be added to matrix materials to make composites. Each of these systems will be looked at in more detail in this paper.

Many people have sought to understand the mechanical properties of cellulose fibres. This presentation will focus on reviewing a few key studies of where ductility is both demonstrated in nature and how it can be replicated (or mimicked) in synthetic system. One issue however with the literature is the liberal use of the word toughness, which is often used to describe the ductility or enhanced strain to failure of a composite system rather than its ability to resist the propagation of cracks. The term ‘work of fracture’ is often more appropriate for relating to ductility and this paper will focus on this property. Work of fracture can be related directly to the toughness, but there are many more mechanisms other than enhanced ‘strain to failure’ that may lead to an increased toughness e.g. crack deflection/deviation, multiple cracking.

One key component of wood’s structure that leads to a high ‘work of fracture’ (which is related to the high strain to failure) is the helically wound microfibrils in the cell wall of the fibres [1]. The helically wound fibrils in the wood cell walls give rise to a pseudo buckling effect in tension, which enhances strain to failure (or ductility) [2]. Most importantly the cell wall thickness plays a key role in determining the onset of buckling and thereby the resistance of the material to failure.

Some plant fibres, particularly the basal regions of the stems of cleavers [2] exhibit very high strains to failure (~20% or more). Goodman remarks that the mechanism responsible for this high strain to failure is unclear, with no apparent relationship to fibril angle [2]. Very high strain to failure in marine kelp (~40%) have been reported [3], an effect that is related to the very high microfibril angles observed (~60°). In petiole tissue in plants such as celery and coir, high strains to failure (~8-10%) are also achieved by very high, almost “spring-like” morphology to the fibres [4]. Changes in the

microfibril angle during deformation have also been identified as a means to obtain plastic deformation behavior beyond the elastic regime, although in some cases (particularly wood) there is even a reversal (elastic recovery) of the material [5].

Structural hierarchy seen in plant tissues, in the form of helically wound “tubes” would be hard to achieve on a mass scale required for commercial composite production. Some attempts to obtain fibres that display helically wound microstructures have however been obtained recently using an electrospinning technique [6]. More recently core-shell fibres have been produced which most closely mimic the primary cell wall (‘random’) orientations of fibrils [7]. These core-shell fibres were formed into sheets (a fibrous network), which displayed strain to failures in excess of 30% [7]. The effect of various morphological features on the mechanics of fibrous networks has been studied in some detail by various authors. Heyden and Gustafsson showed clearly that the ductility of inter-fibre bonds plays a key role in the strain to failure of fibrous networks, as does fibre curl etc. [8]. Negative in-plane Poisson’s ratios of fibrous networks (in this case paper) were predicted by Cox in his classic paper from which most theories of stress transfer in composite materials are derived [9]. Most recently, work by the author and others has shown that nanofibrous networks of cellulose display a small but negative in-plane Poisson’s ratio [10]. Quite how this relates to ductility is not clear but could point the way to forming double curved pre-forms for composite parts. Nanofibrous sheets of cellulose have been shown to display high ductility (strains up to ~10%) [11], which can be preserved to some extent in composite material [12].

Most recently it has been shown that it is possible to effect the properties of the resin material, particularly amorphous polymers, by the inducing of crazing due to the presence of nanocellulose [13] and other components such as clay [14]. Here very large strain to failures can be achieved with a pronounced stress whitening of the sample due to air scattering from the voiding within the craze zones.

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